

2025 NASA SMD Open Source Science Data Repositories Workshop

Minimal Metadata Elements - In-Person
August 25, 2025

- Facilitators: Rebecca Ringuette
- Note-Taker: Rhea Bridgeland
- Chat monitor: Fred Kepner

ALL DAY MATERIALS CAN BE FOUND HERE

Agenda

- Visit each of five activity stations in small groups (online visit breakout rooms)
- A bell will ring to signal change to another station - mix up and join a new group
- Minimal Metadata Elements - *Rebecca Ringuette*

Pre-Activity

Group 3:

- Guest: Is there a reason why they would be different?
 - RR: Yes, we do not have research data []
- Guest: What level of granularity?
 - RR: Data sets. If you want to talk about definitions, we will get to that at the thesaurus group.
- Guest: Isn't all NASA data free?
 - RR: It is all free but some of it is restricted
 - Guest 2: Oh not dealing with ITAR then.
 - RR: No.
 - Guest 3: ITAR data is quarantined off by itself
 - Guest: So free as in to the public or NASA?
 - RR: Free to the public. So if it's always free for the repository you use, then mark it yes.
 - Guest: What agency besides NASA does the funding pertain to?
 - RR: NSF, international members, EU, Japanese gov, etc
 - Guest: That is a weird designation for us.
 - Guest: For PDS, we require most of this...or all of this. For mission and research. So I don't know what to say.
 - G: What is ORCID for NASA authors?
 - RR: So NASA employee or funded by NASA

- G: In PDS we have to list every single author, a relatively new requirement
- G: so sky coordinates, it's not in data sites...
- RR: Not in data sites. This is separate from Data sites, it's what NASA will do.
- G: Temporal could be optional.
- Why is it optional in one and recc in another?
- RR: We get a lot more submissions from missions than research. Can we require something gold standard, or easy and replicable?
- And Mission data will come from the NASA folks, or the PI. If we put too much on them, we won't get 90% of it..

Group 4:

- SS: Many times we get data files, it can be anything, but then nothing tells me how the data is taken. So with VPS, we create a table that tells us this data file had these parameters, the DOI, etc
- RR: That would go under reference publications.
- SS: I will show some examples tomorrow
- JB: Is it worth being specific about the original version?
- RR: Not original software. If someone created a software, that DOI goes there. Just some imbedded linking between publications and software
- SS: Do you have a read me file for the investigators? By type of sample, location, characterization?
- RR: That would be data documentation, so more fine level that what we want here. Those will be more division specific. So this is not trying to get all those details
- SS: We have introduced 4 sections for the PIs to fill out for most of our physical sciences that are hypothesis driven, Hypo, objective, approach, and what kind of impacts do you envision. So I will show it tomorrow. I felt as a scientist, I need to take time to decide if I can spend 2 weeks on something. So I've had people say they like this, because they can quickly read and see if it's something to spend time on.
- SS: What is ROR
- JB: I get it for ORCID, what is publisher ROR.....
- RR: That should be affiliation (NEED TO FIX on poster)
- JB: What do you mean by other creator?
- RR: Anyone who is not a NASA author.
- RR: For VPS, for version, having it be mandatory means it needs to be assigned
- SS: We want to maintain a version for us to look at, and go back and see. But does it need to be available publicly?
- RR: A lot. For transparency. If something gets published on that, and then it's taken down, readers can see what it was. And a minor version wouldn't need a DOI.

Group 1:

- RR: It cannot be recommended as mandatory if it does not exist. We don't want division specific requirements in the recommended section.
- BP: Does it include software?
- RR: Yes. Stuff for software will be a coffee chat
- BH: At the data set collection level?

- RR: Whatever it is you assign the DOI to.
- BH: Platform is a tricky thing.
- RR: Yes, that's why it's not on here. Recommendation is to push for DOIs, if NASA is going to DOI for a mission, once its funded it needs a DOI.
- SL: For us, we would have a mission page with a DOI
- RR: That would be the landing page, and the file for it will be the OSF[]
- BH: The type of platform is of interest maybe?
- RR: That can be pulled in second hand from the DOIs, then if platform type is relevant, that can be a list of keywords to click. If we do it for missions, it can be pulled in or autopop.
- BH: A search engine should be able to make that connection
- RR: I would argue it can't be mandatory. Because missions have simulated data.
- SL: Like a CALVAL [?] campaign would still loosely be mission base
- SL: Like an EVS mission can have an airport, satellite, and ocean component. All types of in-situ. But don't necessarily need that as mandatory metadata at this level.
- SW: Maybe further down than mandatory, but how are variables and parameters tracked?
- RR: Out of scope here. These things are easy and apply everywhere. That is a board concept that could apply, but it would be very demanding. If there is no automated process, it is very demanding. If it can be piped in...
- SW: On the user side, users will look for it based on variable
- RR: Variable type?
- BP: Not platform level. Are you trying to figure out how to categorize CMR fields? Is it for enforcement? All of this is CMR variables.
- RR: This should be across all divisions. If there is a field in here that BPS requires, it will be there.

Group:

- BT: What is between optional and recommended? Why even have optional?
- RR: optional does not apply across all divisions or types of data, or they may be partially hard to do.
- TS: What does data volume mean? Size?
- RR: Yes.
- TS: So it will change.
- TS: What is this assigned to?
- RR: Anything that you assign the DOI to.
- BT: Checksum for file by file.
- RR: No, the whole data set. Whatever you assign the DOI to. NOT file by file.
- BT: I still think volume is reasonable.
- LY and TS: Too many releases, it gets ridiculous.
- RR: But there are concept DOIs.
- LY: DOI was designed for literary papers. Once it's written, it's done. Data is not papers, and should not be handled the same. The standards are flippant.
- RR: Yes, its lacking

- LY: It needs to get defined. When SHOULD a DOI get assigned? There needs to be a better consensus, what should trigger a new DOI?
- RR: First we need to assure we do assign DOI per data set, and versions of data, and divisions need to id what changes are necessary.
- LY: We are versioning all of our data
- RR: And that should stay with the divisions
- JG: For high level searches, what are the models and use cases?
- RR: Hoping earth search engine improves and makes all of this support. Another piece is linen to persistent identifiers. Data has it, instruments will soon. By using this map of identifiers we can track a lot.
- LY: Are you tracking by ORCID?
- RR: People already do
- LY: For themselves, but is NASA?
- RR: I think individually, no. But globally, probably. For proposals and such. And that gets tracked
- LY: Oh, sure.
- RR: We are losing the ability to track, we need to automate.
- LY: In planetary we have solved this ourselves, both mission and research.
- JG: The programmatic data calls we get are all about this (Funding A Numbers)
- BT: This is too far, we want to be sparing here to uniquely identify the bare minimum. So it must be for publishing the data, public notice. It needs to be clarified, Many of these scientific info don't belong here. Subsequent systems should pick this up.
- TS: What is this metadata for
- RR: This comes from the meetings from the past 2 years. What does FAIR mean, how do we measure, how to not burden. The other is the science discovery engine, this feeds into what we think we should require for the research repository Use cases are tracking and interlining. Measuring impact and from the researcher side, how many people are citing, how to reproduce.
- TS: Do these things answer the questions for SCIAX [?] What questions do you expect people to ask EE? So I think temporal and spatial and all that belong here. Like the spatial bounds could = jupiter.
- BT: So still, recommended vs optional?
- RR: The interlinking between the identifiers. Some of this was from conversations